

The Silent Struggle: Unpacking Social Perceptions of Childlessness among Married Couples

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Abstract

The study examined the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society. An objective and one research question alongside one hypothesis were raised for the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A population of 160,301 women in 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was used. A sample of 100 women from 5 communities was used and this was done via multi-stage sampling technique of Random sampling technique and Proportionate sampling technique. The questionnaire titled “Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)” was used as instrument to collect relevant data. The instrument was validated by some experts and its reliability was tested for to be 0.75. The data collected, were analyzed using frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions and Chi-square was used to test for the hypotheses. The findings from the study showed that childlessness brings about a high level of negative social impacts on married couples in diverse ways with mean ($\bar{x} = 3.18$). Based on this, it was recommended that proper awareness should be given to couples as to the factors that are inherent to cause childlessness for them. Also, policies should be generated towards protecting the rights of couples in the society, regardless of what they might be facing.

Introduction

The negative attitudes towards childlessness, especially childless women, have their roots in antiquity. In many cases, those attitudes were supported by existing law. Unfortunately, we can still trace ancient mindsets in the cultures of almost all countries participating in this concept analysis. Maltese figurines of the Goddess of Fertility from the late Neolithic (3000–2500 B.C.) found in hypogea in Malta, as in other prehistoric cultures, represent the importance of praying to the deities from the dawn of humankind to be liberated from the “curse” of childlessness. In Babylon, Assyria, and Egypt, a husband could divorce a wife if she was infertile. Another example is the famous Law of Hammurabi (1750 B.C.). According to it, an infertile woman can give a slave to her husband to “impregnate” (the use of “impregnate” implies that the male is the predominant gender behind a conception, an attitude that held

strongly until very recently, originating from the Vedic traditions according to which, the earth layer of the triparte world was the one (considered the mother) that received the water falling from the Heaven (the invisible layer, the residence of God(s) and considered to be the father) in the form of rain, storm, etc., and then vegetation came out) the child is born, the master's wife raises the child as if her own and the slave gets her freedom for the service to the master. Many of the women in the Bible are described as being barren. In the Old Testament, Abraham's wife "Sarah was barren; she had no child". Sarah encouraged Abraham to have a child with a young woman, Hagar. Rachael asked Jacob to have intercourse with her servant Valla to have a child. Location Uteri (ancient Rome) allowed patricians to have a child through another woman without having to go through the hassle of pregnancy. In Homer, Megapenthes was the child of Menelaos and a slave because the Gods did not give Helen a child. In ancient Sparta, other women were allowed to come and live in the house of the husband to maintain the continuity of the family. Resonating the above-mentioned Babylonian, Assyrian, and Egyptian sources, in old Greek legislative documents, if a woman could not have children, the husband was allowed to have sex with another woman. Initially in Mani and then in other areas in Greece (Trikeri of Thessaly, Kerkyra (Corfu) and Crete) and despite the resistance of the Orthodox Christian Church, we find the practice of *synkria* (syn + *kyria*, *kyra* (συν + κυρία/κυρά)) that was present until the end of the 19th century. According to this practice, when a wife could not have male children or no children at all, her husband could get married to a second woman without getting a divorce first, and the two marriages were both valid. The second wife was called *synkria* (σύνγκρια) or *synkormissa* (συνκόρμισσα) and replaced the first wife in the child-bearing process so that the socially needed male descendant was born. The relevant agreement was even part of a dowry agreement, to which the first wife and the parents of the second one contributed. In Mani, the position of the second wife (*synkria*) was under the condition of the birth of a male child, while the housewife ("mistress of the house") remained the first wife. When the male child was born, the first wife became co-godmother, replacing the biological relation with the spiritual one. However, if the second wife (*synkria*) gave birth to female children, then her daughters were considered inferior to the daughters of the first wife and inherited only the paternal property. In addition, in case the second wife (*synkria*) remained childless, she ran the risk of being kicked out of the house as a sinner or, in the best scenario, she would remain in the house as a "servant" (*ψυχόκορη*).

In the ancient Mesopotamian cuneatic sources, people used infertility to marginalize each other in social life. To prevent the problem of infertility and miscarriage, people prepared drugs using various plants, stones, and minerals, or they resorted to “magic” as a part of the treatment. However, the meaning attributed to the child by the woman and the man was not always positive, in which case the pregnancy was either continued as a conscious choice or otherwise it was terminated, again with the help of herbal drugs.

Childlessness is defined as the absence of children in an individual’s life. Childlessness can be considered involuntary when an individual is unable to have children for medical reasons, whether known or unexplained. According to the World Health Organization, “infertility is a disease of the male or female reproductive system defined by the failure to achieve a pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular unprotected sexual intercourse”. Childlessness can be considered voluntary when a human being deliberately chooses not to have children. A “childfree” definition is usually used in this case. Finally, childlessness can be considered determined by circumstances when the person wants to have children, but the first pregnancy is delayed and, in the long run, is left without children for social or physiological reasons.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

To examine the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society.

Research Question

What are the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses are formulated for the study:

H0₁: There is no significant impact of social perception of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Significance of the Study

To married couples; the findings from this study will aid in the direction of the perception of married couples on the right track towards childlessness and enable them to develop an edge towards seeking for solutions without being stressed.

To family relations; the findings from this study will help in the proper direction of their mindsets as related to childlessness thereby enabling them to be more encouraging rather than discouraging to married couples.

Scope of the Study

This study will strictly focus on examining socio-cultural and childlessness impact on married couples in the society. The target population for this study will comprise of married couples in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Definition of Terms

Childlessness: This refers to the inability of procuring an offspring.

Impact: This refers to the exacerbated influence an entity has on another.

Socio-Cultural Impact: This refers to the influence exerted by the society on another entity socially and culturally.

Married Couples: These are individuals that have decided to imbibe the duty of coming together to live as one legally, traditionally or religiously.

Social Perception towards Childlessness of Married Couples in the Society

The meaning of, and reaction to childlessness is mediated by socio-cultural factors, which vary widely among societies. In Sub Saharan Africa the traditional belief systems based on continuity of lineages place a high premium on fertility (Ibisomi, L., &Mudege, 2014). As a

result the perception of people regarding childlessness especially in a woman, whose primary function is considered childbearing and whose economic and social status is often hinged on their ability to have children, is often derogatory and judgmental. Whatever the cause, as a result of existing social and gender norms, women are often blamed if a couple is childless. Women may suffer any or a combination of the following as a result of being childless - distress, depression, lowered self-esteem, social stigma, open ridicule, isolation, economic deprivation, physical violence, threats from husbands and husbands' family, rejection, abandonment and divorce (Rasak&Oladipo, 2017).

According to Ibisomi and Mudege (2014), childlessness is still not embraced in Nigeria, where pronatalist culture is still very strong. They noted a more tolerant attitude to involuntary childlessness in this study. This may suggest genuine changes or shifts in perception regarding involuntary childlessness. It could also have been influenced by the sequencing of the discussion whereby perception to on voluntary childlessness was first discussed before involuntary childlessness. Further, the openness with which social parenting was discussed and its general acceptability may be positive signs that the negative social consequences that childless individuals suffer in Nigerian societies might be or go on the decline (Rasak&Oladipo, 2017).

In every country of the world, there is a not too silent order for human procreation. This is expressly true of African countries where every couple is expected to desire and bear children. Although many assume childbearing is a natural occurrence, they would spontaneously achieve sometime along their life course, many couples fall short of achieving this through infertility. Infertility, as a reproductive health problem, has the highest-burden on people in developing countries.

In Nigeria, high premium is traditionally placed on having children and this is celebrated in the society by rites and rituals (Nnadi, 2013). Voluntary childlessness is rare with less than one percent of men and women stating zero as their ideal number of children (this most likely includes men and women with confirmed infecundity and that have accepted their status as such). On the other hand, infertility (as defined by the inability of a woman to conceive or carry a pregnancy to full term) among women aged 45-49 years ranged from 3-5% in the country (Botwe, Bamfo-Quaicoe, Hunu,*et al.*, 2015). Infertility was found to be consistently higher in the rural areas compared to the urban and in the North compared to the South.

Relevance of the Psychosocial Theory to the Current Study

Psychosocial theory is a theory that hinges its speculations on the impact that the variables in the society tend to socially and culturally impact on individuals by linking this to the minds of the individuals. It further illustrates the numerous dimensions that are worthy of consideration when dealing with socio-cultural impacts of some basic phenomenon in the society on individuals that are being entangled with it either directly or indirectly. Doing this helps in fostering the basic understanding towards the purpose that is being etched out for this current topic under study. This thereby brings about the much potency of the theories of being adopted for the study.

Theoretical Review

Psychosocial Theory by Erik Erikson

Erik Erikson is the primary theorist identified with the development of psychosocial theory. This chapter focuses on six basic concepts: (a) stages of development, (b) psychosocial crises, (c) the central processes for resolving the psychosocial crisis, (d) the radius of significant

relationships, (e) prime adaptive ego qualities, and (f) core pathologies. Erikson asserts in his psychosocial theory that ego identity is reached by facing goals and challenges throughout eight stages of development over the entire life cycle. Each of the psychosocial stages is distinguished by two opposing emotional forces, known as contrary dispositions that result in a crisis that needs to be resolved. Each crisis must be mastered as swiftly as possible, otherwise, a person's psychology is in jeopardy. However, a successful resolution of the conflict results in a healthy personality and the attainment of a basic virtue. The ego uses these character strengths to resolve subsequent crises.

1. *Identity vs. Role Confusion*

The fifth stage of psychosocial development is marked by an adolescent identity crisis. Between the ages of 12-18, an individual develops a sense of self by experimenting with a variety of social roles. An adolescent who is successful at forming a cohesive, positive identity will have a strong sense of identity, whereas adolescents who do not search for an identity or are pressured into an identity may experience role confusion and develop a weak sense of self. Basic virtue developed: fidelity.

2. **Intimacy vs. Isolation**

The sixth stage extends from late adolescence to early middle age, 18 to 40. A strong sense of self must be developed in adolescence in order to create intimate relationships with others during this stage. Adults who lack a positive self-concept may experience emotional isolation or loneliness.

To avoid feeling isolated or alone, individuals must learn to not lose themselves when sharing or caring for others. Gaining a strong self-identity allows an individual to achieve true intimacy, whereas identity diffusion can be a challenge. Basic virtue developed: love.

3. Generativity vs. Stagnation

Also called generativity versus self-absorption, the seventh stage in Erikson's psychosocial development theory occurs during the ages of 40-65. During middle adulthood, individuals have a positive goal of generativity. In most cases, this results in procreation, along with the fulfillment of parental and social responsibilities. This is in strict contrast to interest in the self or self-absorption. Basic virtue developed: care.

4. Integrity vs. Despair

The final stage of psychosocial development theory during old age (65+) is a period when a person reflects on life. One can either develop a sense of satisfaction with their life and approach death with peace or develop a sense of despair over missed opportunities and wasted time, leaving the individual to approach death with dread. Basic virtue developed: wisdom.

Methodology

Research Design

The design of this study is the descriptive research design. This design is that which employs both qualitative and quantitative data for the proper dissemination of the stated questions that are formulated to dissolve the major purpose for this study. This research design was chosen because of the purpose of the study to gather information on socio-cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Population of the Study

The population for this study will comprise of women present in the 65 communities in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, which constitutes to a total estimation of 160,301 women (National Population Census, (2008) and World Sex Ratio (2021)).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique of random sampling technique and proportionate sampling technique will be used for sample selection. Random sampling technique will be used in the selection of 5 communities out of the 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. Proportionate sampling technique will then be adopted in the selection of 20 women each in the chosen communities. A total sample of 100 women will then be given and used for the study, as stipulated in the table below:

Table 1: Sample Distribution

S/N	Districts	Sample Chosen
1	Choba	20
2	Rumueme	20
3	Ozuoba	20
4	Rumuokoro	20
5	Rumuigbo	20
Total		100

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument employed in this study is the questionnaire. It is a 20-item self-structure instrument titled “**Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)**” that will be partitioned into two sections (A and B). Section A

will cover the demographic aspect of it, which collects personal information about the respondents, while section B will cover the items, which elicited the responses of the respondents on each of the item statements present. The items are responded to with the aid of 4-point Likert scale of measurement of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Method of Data Collection

Data will be collected using questionnaires. The researcher will go to the field and meet up with respondents, then hand out the copies of the questionnaire to them. These respondents will be given directives on how to go about the filling of the distributed instrument. After completion, the researcher will proceed to retrieve the distributed instrument immediately.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Face and content validity of the instrument will be established by giving it to my supervisor and two other lecturers in the Department of Sociology. Their inputs will be ratified further by the supervisor, before its incorporation in the production the final draft of the questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument will be done through the test-retest method. This method is that which involves the administration of the instrument to a selected group of 20 women (outside the sample of the study but within the population of the study) with a separating time difference of 10 days between the two administrations. The responses gotten from the two administrations will then be compared and correlated through the adoption of Pearson Product Moment Correlation, so as to arrive at the reliability co-efficient index of 0.75.

Method of Data Analysis

The data will be subjected to an analytical procedure with the aid of frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions. Chi-square will be used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion-mean will be calculated for as follows:

Strongly Agree (SA) - 4points

Agree (A) - 3points

Disagree (D) - 2points

Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1point

$$\text{Criterion mean} = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

The item with a mean score that is up to and above the criterion mean will be “accepted” while the one with a mean score that is below the criterion mean will be “rejected”.

Results and Discussion

Results

Demographic Analysis

Table 1: Frequency and percentage of the demographics of women

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-29yrs	30	30%
30-39yrs	45	45%
40-49yrs	25	25%
50yrs & above	0	0%
Marital Status		
Single	25	25%

Married	55	55%
Divorced	15	15%
Widowed	5	5%
Separated	0	0%

From the analysis done above, it was displayed that 30% of the total sampled women are of 20-29yrs, 45% of the total sampled women are of 30-39yrs, 25% of the total sampled women are of 40-49yrs; 25% of the total sampled women are single, 55% of the total sampled women are married, 15% of the total sampled women are divorced while 5% of the total sampled women are widowed.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question: What are the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society?

Table 2: Mean statistics displaying the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Remark
1	Childlessness is as a result of wayward living in the past.	31 (124)	45 (135)	14 (28)	10 (10)	2.97	Accepted
2	Childlessness is a form of punishment for the misdeeds of people to others.	28 (112)	39 (117)	20 (40)	13 (13)	2.82	Accepted

3	Childlessness is begotten from the level of impotency of couples in the society.	34 (136)	46 (138)	15 (30)	5 (5)	3.09	Accepted
4	Childlessness is to be linked with diabolical problems surrounding any couple in the society.	32 (128)	50 (150)	15 (30)	3 (3)	3.11	Accepted
Grand Mean						3	High

Data in the table above displayed the mean responses of the women on the social perceptions of childlessness towards married couples in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 2.97, 2.82, 3.09 and 3.11 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained as 3, it can therefore be deduced that there is a high level of negative social perception towards childlessness of married couples in the society.

Discussion of Findings

Childlessness has been regarded as a not positive venture for most couples in the society and majority of them would love to avert things in a way that will be susceptible by them in the society. These lingering issues as regards to childlessness can be linked to some undeserving factors that can be socially and culturally associated. From the analysis done in Tables 1, it was revealed therein that childlessness brings about a high level of negative social impacts on married couples in diverse ways and that there is a high level of negative cultural perception attributed to childlessness of married couples in the society.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Proper awareness should be given to couples as to the factors that are inherent to cause childlessness for them.
- 2) Policies should be generated towards protecting the rights of couples in the society, regardless of what they might be facing.

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